

Insect resistance

Screening for leaffolder resistance

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Thirty-one rice varieties were screened in fields at Pattambi for leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée resistance.

Varieties received through international collaborative projects were planted in 5-m rows at 25 × 25 cm spacing.

Susceptible variety Jaya was planted in border rows. Susceptible check was TN1. Periodic observations started when TN1 plants showed 40% attacked leaves. When the test varieties were scored, TN1 had 68.8% attacked leaves. Resistance rating by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice was based on the corrected percentage of damage.

GEB24 and PTB33 were highly resistant. TKM6, IR21937-26-2-3, Sri Lankan varieties BG12-1, BG367-3, BG379-2, and Thai variety BKNBR1030-51-1-1-2-1 were also resistant (see table). All other varieties were susceptible or highly susceptible. □

Resistance of rice varieties to leaffolder, Pattambi, Kerala, India.

Score ^a	Variety	Origin
1	GEB24, PTB33	India
3	BG12-1, BG367-3, BG379-2	Sri Lanka
	BKNBR1030-51-1-1-2-1	Thailand
	IR21937-26-2-3	IRRI
	TKM6	India
5	BR220-1-1	Bangladesh
	Chianung 51-P1-66-1020	Taiwan, China
	IR21929-12-3-3,)	
	IR21931-47-3-3,)	IRRI
	IR9209-26-2-2-3)	
	Kannagi, T2005	India
7	IR13429-170-3,)	
	IR19575-65-2-2-3)	IRRI
	Kaohsiung Senyw 204	Taiwan, China
	OR100-25, OR55-9,)	
	TNAU9039-14,)	
	TNAU9227-1,)	India
	UPR311-19-2-1,)	
	UPR82-1-7, W1263)	
9	NR59, RNR67580	India
	Surya medal (12923)	Indonesia
	X2-0-1., 343-0.1.	Vietnam
	TN1	Taiwan, China

^a Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Deep water

Screening rice varieties for deepwater tolerance

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More than 12,000 ha of rice lands in Tamil Nadu are submerged or flooded for up to 4 months, Sep-Jan, during the vegetative phase. Local varieties TNR1 and TNR2 yield from 0.8 to 1.0 t/ha.

Twenty-four varieties from the Tamil Nadu Agricultural University germplasm collection were screened at IRRI for various characters that contribute to deepwater tolerance: submergence toler-

ance, salt tolerance, elongation ability, nodal rooting, and kneeing ability.

Submergence tolerance. Ten-day-old seedlings planted in trays were submerged (30 cm) in a water tank along with the check varieties FR13A (resistant) and IR42 (susceptible). Water temperature was maintained at 30°C and light intensity at 400 lux at the tray level. Trays were removed after 7 days and plants were scored 5 days after removal.

Submergence tolerance scores indicated that only TNR1, Dhanya, and Birpak had some degree of tolerance. Submergence tolerance, therefore, does not seem to be a crucial limiting factor for varietal development in deepwater.

Salt tolerance. Seedlings were grown in normal culture solution and transplant-

ed to saline soil with E. C. 9 mS/cm. Subsequent irrigation was with normal water. Cultivars were scored for salinity tolerance 4 weeks after transplanting (see table). TNR1, Ponkambi samba, Kattuvanam, Kar paddy, Dulai Baron, Kala or Black Aman, and Ponni showed tolerance equal to that of the check variety Pokkali.

Elongation ability. Four-week-old seedlings raised in small plastic pots were submerged in 40-cm water. Water level was increased to 90 cm at a rate of 10 cm/day and maintained for 1 week. Plants were removed and height, number of elongated internodes, and nodal rooting were recorded (see table). Elongation varied from 17 to 65 cm (25 to 129% increase). TNR1 and Ponkambi samba had maximum elongation ability. Chingair and Birpak had more